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**Investigating the Impact of Task-Based Language Teaching to Enhance Writing Skills
of Undergraduate Students**

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to investigate the impact of Task-Based Language Teaching on writing skills of undergraduate students. To conduct this quantitative study, forty undergraduate students from 4th semester of English Department were taken as sample. A writing test was taken as tool to collect data from students. Writing test was used as pretest and posttest to analyze the differences in the performance of participants. The focus of this study was on five domains of writing: content, organization, grammar, vocabulary, and mechanics. Data were analyzed using SPSS while applying Paired Sample t-test. Statistical values computed through SPSS indicated that TBLT has more impact on content and grammar while it showed less impact on organization, vocabulary, and mechanics in writing of undergraduate students. Overall findings computed through SPSS suggested positive effect of TBLT on writing skills of undergraduate students. In the light of these findings, TBLT has been recommended to be implemented as a regular technique to improve the writing skills of students.

Keywords: Task-Based Language Teaching, Writing Skills, Instructional Design Theory

Introduction

In second language learning, writing is the most important skill. In the academic context, it is still the most challenging aspect for learners to develop this skill efficiently. Despite being taught for years, a lot of undergraduate students face difficulties in using suitable vocabulary, correcting grammar, and organizing ideas. Undergraduate students are being taught different courses of General English, Functional English, and Expository writing courses in their initial semesters. Traditional lecture method is proven to be unsuccessful in fulfilling this task of developing writing competence among students. Task-based language teaching; on the other hand, focuses more on the involvement of students in the process of skill development. Not only does it increase communicative competence of students but also autonomy of learners.

In Pakistan, English holds the status of official language while Urdu is recognized as the national language. Being a multilingual country, several different languages are spoken in different provinces of Pakistan. These languages include Sindhi, Pashto, Punjabi, Balochi, and Saraiki. Several dialects, vernaculars, and accents are also being spoken in different regions of Pakistan. Since the emergence of Pakistan as an independent state in 1947, English has dominated the highest number of English-medium schools. The reason behind this situation is less trained teachers of the English subject and the poor quality of education. Students are being taught this subject using the traditional method of memorization and imitation. To resolve such problems, English was required to be taught as a compulsory subject from class one onwards, as per the directions of the National Education Policy in the social context. Students from Pakistani public schools are observed as less literate in the English language and are not as capable of social mobility as students of non-elite and elite Policy (NEP 2009) of Pakistan. Furthermore, this policy extended its recommendations by implementing English medium instruction from class four onwards in public schools of Pakistan (Channa, 2017).

In Pakistani public universities, most of the students belong to the background of middle-class societies. Their family background ensures that their mother tongue is mostly regional language. Although English is recognized as the official language of Pakistan and as the medium of instruction in public and private educational sectors, students still face challenges in developing

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competence in this language. In English language classrooms, teachers are not fully trained to incorporate engaging strategies to overcome the problems of English language skills. Among all four skills of language, writing is considered the most difficult one. In the English language, students mostly struggle with writing skills. Prevailing problems of coherence, organization, sentence structure, and suitable use of language in academic contexts are being faced by students. Such problems are raised due to inappropriate practice, lack of interactive teaching methodologies, shortage of vocabulary, and lack of proper feedback on their writing content. Mostly, problems like stating and understanding academic material in the English language are encountered by students who mainly belong to Urdu-medium backgrounds. They find it hard to develop grammar, vocabulary, and to convey difficult ideas, which in turn lead to poor performance in their academics (Qureshi et al., 2025). The gap between the linguistic abilities of learners and their performance criteria is created by the aggravation in these problems due to insufficiency of English language in day-to-day routine (Nadeem, 2024).

As writing is one of the language skills that is most challenging among all, despite being enrolled in different writing courses, students find it difficult to write with accuracy. Although several courses of writing are taught to undergraduate students in initial semesters, the lecture method in teaching writing courses proved to be lacking in developing their skills in writing. Numerous studies have been conducted on the role of *TBLT* in developing the writing skills of students. This research chiefly aims to focus on the advanced academic writing of undergraduate students where they are asked to write for practical concerns. The aim of this study is to examine the role of *TBLT* strategies in improving the writing skills of undergraduate students. In this regard, following major research question has been generated.

- How does *TBLT* affect the writing skills of undergraduate students?

To justify the major research question, following subsidiary research questions have been generated:

- What is the effect of *TBLT* on the content of writing of undergraduate students?
- What is the effect of *TBLT* on the organization of writing of undergraduate students?
- What is the effect of *TBLT* on the grammar of undergraduate students?
- What is the effect of *TBLT* on the vocabulary of undergraduate students?
- What is the effect of *TBLT* on the mechanics of undergraduate students?

Literature Review

The incorporation of various tasks to enhance language development is a key concern in task-based language teaching. It was first proposed in the 1980s and 1990s (Long, 1985; Long & Crookes, 1992, 1993; Nunan, 1989; Robinson, 1994, 1998; Skehan, 1996). Interest in the introduction of tasks in *TBLT* has grown gradually over the past twenty years, following a slow start. This approach, which recently grew out of the Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) is called task-based language teaching. Norris (2011) defined *TBLT* as an approach to foreign or second language studies which connects empirical and theoretical foundations for good teaching, giving more focus on concrete learning outcomes in the form of ‘tasks’—to analyze what learners are able to do with the language” (p. 578). Experiential Learning Theory (ELT) also highlighted that learning outcomes in the process of language learning can be improved by the involvement of learners in the process (Dewey, 1938; Kolb, 1984).

According to Shehadeh (2005), *TBLT* is not a new approach for language teaching; rather, it has been in place for more than three decades. The commitment of *TBLT* to accentuate the importance of tasks linked to learners’ daily experiences, increasing their comprehension for the target language, ensures its effectiveness (Alam et al., 2018b; Ellis, 2003). Ellis et al. (2020) highlighted the value of both sociocultural and cognitive perspectives for *TBLT*. The view of

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cognitive-interactionists suggests that Second Language Acquisition (SLA) occurs when students focus on meaning and form while receiving input. From a sociocultural perspective, the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) plays an essential role and learning is enhanced through interaction.

A number of studies have discussed the significance of teaching and learning the writing process with the help of practical insights. A study conducted (Barkaoui, 2007) offered a detailed overview of findings from foreign language (L2) writing research and theory, with the main focus on the kinds of skills that learners are supposed to acquire for effective writing. Barkaoui reinforced the importance to understand various elements of linguistics that include vocabulary, syntax, grammar, lexicon, rhetorical discourse, and conventions of a second language. A study conducted on the B.com students of Government College of Commerce, Khanewal, revealed that TBLT was a significant approach in enhancing their writing competence. The pre-test and post-test results, analyzed by applying chi-square and weighted average, confirmed the improvement in the writing performance of students. (Rubab et al., 2014). AS well Ghani & Rubab (2014) analysed the writing skills of social sciences students and suggested a writing based EAP course.

Benlaghrissi and Ouahidi (2024) investigated that TBLT and mobile-assisted language learning (MALL) enhance EFL learners' paragraph writing. Their exposure of vocabulary, ideas, and content, grammar, mechanics, and organization had a positive effect by the use of these approaches. WhatsApp based tasks were being introduced in their classrooms for the experimental group only. So, the findings proved the collaboration of TBLT and MALL as a significant approach for the improvement of paragraph writing of students.

As seen in previous researches, TBLT has proven its positive influence on the writing skills of students. Different researches have been done on different aspects of writing skills, such as paragraph writing, essay writing, and story writing etc. The present research is solely concerned with a course of Advanced Academic Reading and Writing. As the focus of this study was only writing skills, the topics of the writing section were followed by the researcher, leaving the reading portion.

Theoretical Framework

Instructional Design Theory (Reigeluth & Carr-Chelmann, 2009) claims to give practically achievable, experimentally researchable, and theoretically motivated criteria for sequencing and grading tasks. This theory holds three main components.

- The Cognition Hypothesis
- The Triadic Componential Framework
- SSARC model

The Cognition Hypothesis (Robinson, 2001b, 2003a), which has been the foundation of growing empirical research in the modern era, proposes the theoretical motivation for the claims of task sequencing. A framework known as Triadic Componential Framework (Robinson, 2001a, 2005, 2007a) supports these claims that are possible to be carried out in the real contexts to categorize the features of task designing, and the SSARC Model (Robinson, 2010, 2015) offers a step-by-step guide for combining features of task design (given in the framework of Triadic Componential) to gradually make the instructional tasks more complex in their cognitive ability.

The effectiveness of TBLT in developing different skills of language has been proved by a number of studies. There are a number of international research studies that highlight the importance of TBLT in facilitating autonomy of learners and communicative competence, but limited research is being done on how the complexity of tasks influences writing performance. Moreover, a few studies have used Instructional Design Theory as a theoretical framework to

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design tasks for writing. This study focuses to analyze how TBLT under the influence of Instructional Design Theory can improve the writing skills of undergraduate students.

Hypotheses

H₀¹: TBLT has no significant effect on the undergraduate students' writing skills.

H₁¹: TBLT significantly improves the writing skills of undergraduate students.

H₀²: TBLT has no significant effect on the content of writing of undergraduate students.

H₁²: Task-Based Language Teaching significantly improves the content of the writing of undergraduate students.

H₀³: TBLT has no significant effect on the organization of writing of undergraduate students. H₁³: Task-Based Language Teaching significantly improves the organization of the writing of undergraduate students

H₀⁴: TBLT has no significant effect on the grammar of undergraduate students

H₁⁴: Task-Based Language Teaching significantly improves the grammar of undergraduate students

H₀⁵: TBLT has no significant effect on the vocabulary of undergraduate students

H₁⁵: Task-Based Language Teaching significantly improves the vocabulary of undergraduate students

H₀⁶: TBLT has no significant effect on the mechanics of undergraduate students

H₁⁶: Task-Based Language Teaching significantly improves the mechanics of undergraduate students

Research Methodology

This study used a quantitative approach with a quasi-experimental research design. Only one group of forty students from 4th semester of English department was selected using intact group sampling technique to participate in this research study. These participants were selected from Government Graduate College Pasrur, District Sialkot. Research tool used to collect data was a writing test designed by researcher herself. The test was conducted in two phases as the pre-test and the post-test. The purpose of these tests was to assess the writing performance of students before and after the intervention. Moreover, the tests were divided into three sections namely, summarization of academic articles, report writing, and synthesis and analysis of academic content aligned with the topics of the course outline. Post-test was designed with minor differences from the pre-test. Brown's writing model (2007) was used to evaluate the writing test. The collected data were analyzed quantitatively using SPSS to describe the results and findings of this study.

Findings and Results

The analysis of both pretest and posttest scores was conducted on SPSS through a Paired Sample T-test. This statistical method is significant to compare the means of the pretest and posttest. Firstly, the mean and standard deviation of both pretest and posttest scores were measured to analyze the general trend in the performance of the same group of participants. Furthermore, paired sample t-test provided t-value, degrees of freedom (df) and significance value (p-value). As the writing test comprised 3 questions, the scores of the pretest and posttest for all three questions were considered separately in a paired sample t-test analysis. This means that the overall scoring of writing skills was computed using SPSS. The following table shows the findings of paired sample statistics.

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H_0 : TBLT has no significant effect on the writing skills of undergrad students.

Table 1: Showing results of Paired Sample Statistics

Paired Samples Statistics

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
Pair 1	Summarization	6.0719	40	1.16571	.18432
	Summarization	7.5595	40	1.08703	.17188
Pair 2	Report Writing	6.2626	40	1.03191	.16316
	Report Writing	7.3034	40	.85927	.13586
Pair 3	Synthesis & Analysis	6.4656	40	.69625	.11009
	Synthesis & Analysis	7.3469	40	.66173	.10463

The given table gives a detailed descriptive comparison of scores of pretest and posttest for all three writing tasks. The difference in the mean value for pair 1 shows the improvement of 1.49 points after the intervention of *TBLT*. The decrease in the value of the standard deviation indicates the consistency in the scores. In case of report writing, the given table indicates that increase in the value of mean by 1.04 points, reduction in the value of standard deviation and decrease in the value of standard error mean suggest strong accuracy in the average scores of participants. For the third pair of synthesis and analysis, an increment of 0.88 points in the mean value, a slight change in the value of standard deviation, and a decrease in the standard error mean support consistency in the improvement of scores of the posttest. For all three questions of writing test, descriptive statistics suggests overall improvement in the scores of the posttest due to the intervention of task-based activities.

Another table computed on SPSS shows paired sample t-test analysis of writing test scores. This table again illustrates the mean difference values, standard deviation values, and p-values for each question separately. The table given below shows all these findings.

Table 2: Showing results of Paired Sample T-Test

Paired Differences

95% Confidence Interval of the difference

		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Lower	Upper	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Pair 1	Summarization	-	.80786	.12773	-	-	-	39	<.001
	Summarization	1.48762			1.74599	1.22926	11.646		
Pair 2	Report Writing	-	.58806	.09298	-	-.85268	-	39	<.001
	Report Writing	1.04075			1.22882		11.193		
Pair 3	Synthesis & Analysis	-.88125	.61885	.09785	-	-.68333	-9.006	39	<.001
	Synthesis & Analysis				1.07197				

This table shows the comparative analysis of the performance of students in all three questions of

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the writing test before and after an intervention. For the first pair of summarization, the mean difference value of -1.48762 indicates an increase in scores of the posttest. The t-value of -11.646 and p-value <0.001 suggest that improvement after intervention is quite significant. For report writing, the mean difference value of -1.04075, the t-value of -11.193, and the p-value <0.001 indicate a significant statistical improvement. The mean difference value of -0.88125, t-value of -9.006, and p-value of <0.001 for synthesis and analysis prove a positive shift in the writing performance of students.

H02: TBLT has no significant effect on the content of undergrad students' writing.

The increase in the mean value of content from pretest to posttest (8.23-9.85) shows a positive effect of the intervention for content development. The decrease in the value of the standard deviation gives consistency in the pretest and posttest scores of the same participant.

H03: TBLT has no significant effect on the organization of the writing of undergrad students.

For the second pair of organizations, an increase in the mean value from pretest to protest (5.22-5.68) shows a moderate change in it. This slight change indicates improvement in the structure of the content.

H04: TBLT has no significant effect on the grammar of undergraduate students' writing.

In case of grammar, the shift of mean value from pretest to posttest (4.47-5.92) shows significant enhancement, suggesting strong grammatical accuracy. The reduction in the value of standard deviation (0.99-0.59) further confirms reduced variation in scores.

H05: TBLT has no significant effect on the vocabulary of undergraduate students' writing.

For the fourth pair of vocabulary, the change in mean value (3.83-4.36) from pretest to posttest shows a significant gain in the use of vocabulary. Furthermore, a decrease in the standard deviation value (0.59-0.43) suggests consistency among participants.

H06: TBLT has no significant effect on the mechanics of writing of undergraduate students.

Shift in the mean value (3.56-4.01) from pretest to posttest for mechanics indicates enhancement in the correct use of capitalization, spelling, and punctuation. Meanwhile, a reduction in the standard deviation (0.62-0.57) from pretest to posttest confirms uniform learning outcomes. So, the statistics analysis suggests that task-based language teaching has a positive impact on all five components of writing.

Finally, the last table for paired sample t-test analysis given below shows mean, standard deviation, t-values and p-values for all five components of writing.

Table 3: Showing Paired Sample T-Test Analysis of Writing Components

		Paired Samples Test							
		Mean	St. Deviation	St. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of Difference				
					Lower	Upper	t	df	Sig
Pair 1	Pretest scores of content Posttest scores of content	-1.662500	1.07864	.17055	-1.9997	-1.28003	-9.528	39	<.001

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Pair 2	Pretest scores of organization Posttest scores of organization	-.46600	.7114	.11244	-.9343	-.23857	-4.144	39	<.001
Pair 3	Pretest scores of grammar Posttest scores of grammar	- 1.144975	.75267	.11901	- 1.69046	- 1.20904	-12.182	39	<.001
Pair 4	Pretest scores of vocabulary Posttest scores of vocabulary	-.53750	.47214	.07465	-.68850	-.38650	-7.200	39	<.001
Pair 5	Pretest scores of mechanics Posttest scores of mechanics	-.42500	.58342	.09225	-.61159	-.23841	-4.07	39	<.001

In the first pair, the mean difference value between pretest and posttest scores for content is -1.625, t-value -9.528, and p-value <0.001, which shows that scores of posttest were significantly higher than pretest. According to the guidelines given by Cohen, all these values show a large effect size, indicating strong improvement (Cohen, 1988). For the organization, the mean difference value of -4.66, t-value of -4.144, and p-value <0.001 indicate improvement in scores of the posttest. These values for organization suggest a small effect size as compared to other areas of writing. Mean difference value of -1.449, t-value of -12.182, and p-value <0.001 indicate a large effect size for grammar. This means that this component of writing is effectively improved after intervention. In the case of vocabulary, the mean difference value of -0.53, t-value of -7.20, and p-value <0.001 show improvement in this area. For the last pair of mechanics, the mean difference value of -0.425, the t-value of -4.607, and p-value <0.001 indicate improvement in this skill of writing, although less in magnitude in comparison to other components of writing. Overall, statistics suggest that task-based language teaching has a positive impact on all five components of writing.

The findings of this study have been explained on the basis of the analysis. The findings display the justification of the major and subsidiary research questions. The major and subsidiary research questions to align with the findings of this portion.

Impact of TBLT on Writing Components

The major research question is about the effect of TBLT on the writing skills of undergraduate students to find whether this learner-centered approach overcomes their writing challenges or not. This first question gives the key findings, describing how this task-based approach has improved the writing skills of students relating to the topics of their course outline. This first research question is given as follows:

Statistical descriptions for the portion of summarization suggest that intervention of task-based activities significantly improves the ability to write summaries of articles. The findings of this present study align with the results of the study conducted by Hasbi et al. (2023). This previous study used a classroom action research design in which students significantly improved their language structure and organization of ideas. Moreover, the implementation of task-based activities also enhanced the independence of students and their interaction in learning.

For report writing, increase in the mean value by 1.04 points, reduction in the value of standard deviation and decrease in the value of standard error mean suggest strong accuracy in the average scores of participants. A study held by Raut, S. (2019) concluded that students of grade eight showed improvement in their written expression and arranging their ideas in writing. This research shows alignment with the present study in improving the essay writing and report writing skills of students. The findings of both these studies indicate that TBLT not only enhances the writing skills of undergraduate students but also improves the writing of middle school students.

For the third question of synthesis and analysis of academic material, an increment of 0.88 points in the mean value, and a slight change in the value of standard deviation indicate improvement in the performance of students. The value of the mean in comparison to the other two questions in the test shows weak performance of students in the synthesis and analysis of academic material. These findings hold alignment with the Cognition Hypothesis mentioned in the section of theoretical framework. Writing performance of undergraduate students after being engaged in task-based activities shows that their writing developed due to participation in cognitively designed tasks. Students performed their tasks with organization, strong decision making, and active reasoning, which enhanced their grammatical accuracy, structure, and meaningful expression in writing. This output confirms that such cognitively engaging activities encourage students to produce meaningful writing.

Statistical values of mean difference (-1.625) and significance ($p < 0.001$) computed by SPSS using paired sample t-test indicate improvement in the content of students' writing. Reading and discussion of different articles in pair groups, enlisting of phrases in different texts, and revision of written content with peer groups show development in the content of students' writing. Moreover, discussion in pair groups to perform the main task enhances the cognitive ability of students in writing development. Siraj and Rahman (2025) also executed a quasi-experimental study to analyze the improvement in descriptive writing skills of students. The results revealed that students developed their content in writing due to the implementation of task-based language teaching. This concludes that TBLT plays its role in developing the content of students in their writing.

The findings related to the organization in students' writing provide insights into the positive influence of TBLT on it. This suggests that the increment in the improvement of the organization in their writing is less than in the content. For the organization, the mean difference value of -4.66 and p-value < 0.001 indicate improvement in scores of the posttest. These values for organization suggest a small effect size as compared to other domains of writing skills. While performing various main-tasks, enlisting ideas, making outlines, creating planners for report writing, arrangement of arguments in analyzing different texts, and combining different sources for synthesis enhanced students' organization in their writing. However, findings reveal that improvement in this area of writing is less than the improvement in content.

Grammar is one of the most challenging areas for students in their writing. Statistical description exposed that the change in mean value from pretest to posttest (4.47-5.92) indicates significant enhancement, suggesting strong grammatical accuracy. Using a paired sample t-test, the mean difference value of -1.449 and p-value < 0.001 indicate a large effect size for grammar. This means that this component of writing is effectively improved after intervention.

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In the pre-task stage, listing of phrases, making short sentences in pair groups, and highlighting different sentence structures in given articles improved the grammatical accuracy of students. In the main-task phase, writing of summaries and reports in a limited time span, individually or within groups, and proofreading and peer review feedback in the post-task phase, highly influenced the grammar of students. Among all five components of writing, grammar is the most influential area of writing because of task-based language teaching. Engagement of students in different tasks within pair groups encouraged students to develop their writing in terms of grammar. The enhancement in students' grammatical forms is also justified by the claim of the Cognition Hypothesis that focuses on the participants' concern to form, along with meaning by active involvement in tasks that were cognitively demanding. Their engagement in different writing tasks is also boost by their abilities to self-correct their errors in grammar within pair-groups. Findings of another study indicated the effectiveness of task-based language teaching in improving their grammar. Their average posttest scores (81.4) increased from pretest scores (65.8), which suggests a clear enhancement in their grammar (Rum & Hambali, 2023).

Another important area in writing is vocabulary. The statistical findings related to vocabulary, for example, the mean difference value of -0.53 and p-value <0.001, show improvement in this area. Reading of various texts, extracting important ideas from texts, discussion of writing topics in groups, listing of different transitions and phrases, and choosing the most relevant words to make short sentences were a number of tasks performed by participants that improved their word choices.

The overall findings provide insights that task-based language teaching has improved the word choice of undergraduate students. The vocabulary of research participants was developed through contextual learning and the repeated use of new words while reading various articles.

The last question addresses the impact of task-based language teaching on the mechanics of undergraduate students. In the pre-test, most of the participants made mistakes in capitalization, wrong use of punctuation marks, and misspellings. The mean difference value (-0.425) and significance value less than 0.001 indicate improvement in this skill of writing, although less in magnitude in comparison to other components of writing. Students' revision of writing content within groups during the post-task phase encouraged them to focus on these aspects of mechanics. During the period of intervention of task-based language teaching, it was also observed that students found this phase of correction as a delightful pursuit. The repeating activity of revising and proofreading for punctuation, misspellings, and capitalization improved their mechanics.

Due to their active participation in revising and editing of written material in the post-task stage, they scored high in mechanics in the post-test. Rum and Hambali (2023) also investigated that students in grade ten showed a significant increase in their average scores of mechanics from pretest to posttest. Students' engagement in task-based activities improved their average scores of mechanics from 64.0 to 83.0.

Conclusion

In a nutshell, findings related to the writing test suggest that task-based language teaching has effectively enhanced the overall writing skills of undergraduate students. High statistical values indicate that TBLT significantly showed its impact on the content and grammar of undergraduate students. However, low statistical values of vocabulary, organization, and mechanics, as compared to grammar and content, show that the effect of TBLT is less on them. Overall performance of students in their writing was observed to be high due to their meaningful involvement in cognitively demanding tasks. Their ideas in writing content were refined due to their discussion in pair groups. Furthermore, their five domains of writing considered in this research were effectively improved due to working in collaboration with one another. So, this

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learner-centered approach, contrastive to the traditional method of teaching writing, encouraged students to overcome their challenges in writing. To better develop this approach in writing classes, teachers are to be trained to cope with the challenges of introducing different task-based activities. Future researches should focus on students of non-English department where English writing courses are being taught as minor courses. Furthermore, a comparative research study should be conducted to analyze the differences in the impact of Task-Based Language Teaching on students of English and non-English departments.

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